

JOINT CARRIER PHASE AND FREQUENCY OFFSET TRACKING IN OFDM SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we study an OFDM system subject to carrier phase noise and frequency offset. Contrary to many previous approaches, we assume that the carrier phase and frequency offset are drifting. A scheme for joint estimation of the transmitted sequence and tracking of the carrier phase and frequency offset is presented. The proposed iterative scheme is based on the ECM algorithm - an extension of the EM algorithm - and it performs the joint estimation in a unified manner by, as it turns out, interconnecting an Extended Kalman Smoother with Yule-Walker type equations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) has gained increasing interest over the last decade. It has proven to be highly suitable for transmission in systems that are subject to severe fading and impulse noise. The key idea is that the available spectrum is divided into several narrowband subchannels that are experiencing almost flat fading. Furthermore, the frequency responses of the subchannels are chosen such that they are overlapping and orthogonal in order to achieve a high spectral efficiency of the system. OFDM is today accepted as an effective technique for digital audio broadcasting (DAB), digital video broadcasting (DVB) and digital high-definition television (HDTV) [1, 2, 3].

Unfortunately, the OFDM system is shown to be very sensitive to carrier phase noise and frequency offset. These system impairments are caused by mismatches in the transceiver and receiver oscillators. Assuming a non-dispersive channel, the

channel shift and frequency offset are identical for all carriers. Previous work on carrier phase synchronization and frequency offset estimation can be found in *e.g.* [4, 5, 8, 6, 7]. In [8], a joint maximum likelihood (ML) frequency offset and symbol-time estimator is proposed. [4] applies the expectation maximization (EM) algorithm which estimates the phase rotations of each subcarrier iteratively assuming unknown data signals. In [7], synchronization requirements for an OFDM system is discussed and it is here concluded that an acceptable system must provide an accuracy of the frequency synchronization within 2%.

In this paper, we propose a unified approach for estimation of the transmitted sequence, tracking of the carrier phase error and the frequency offset based on the Expectation Conditional Maximization (ECM) algorithm. It turns out that the carrier phase noise and the frequency offset are jointly estimated via the Extended Kalman Smoother (EKS). As a bi-product of the expectation step of the EM algorithm, we achieve estimates of the transmitted data. The unknown parameters characterizing the fading behavior of the carrier phase noise and the frequency offset are estimated in the maximization step in a maximum a posteriori (MAP) sense via Yule-Walker type equations.

2 PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

2.1 OFDM System

In this paper, we consider an OFDM system subject to carrier phase noise and frequency offset. Consider Fig. 1. Basically, our system description is an extended version of [5]. A serial stream of *unknown* M -PSK data are transmitted at a rate of $1/T_s$. The data are grouped into blocks of length N . Each block is fed into an inverse discrete Fourier

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transform (IDFT) creating N -dimensional blocks. Let c_k^l denote the data in channel l at time k which is modulated with a rectangular pulse $p(t)$ of duration T_s . The signal is transmitted over a *known* multipath channel, h , and subject to carrier phase offset, ϕ , and carrier frequency offset, ϵ . The received baseband signal can be expressed as

$$r(t) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{l=0}^{N-1} c_k^l e^{j2\pi \frac{lt}{T_s}} h(t) e^{j\phi(t)} e^{j2\pi\epsilon(t)t} p(t - kT_s) + n(t), \quad (1)$$

where n is complex-valued additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN). Similarly to [5], we assume that the received symbol in channel l at time k is equal to

$$\hat{c}_k^l = c_k^l |I_l| + \left(\sum_{m=0, m \neq l}^{N-1} c_k^m I_{l-m} + n_k^l \right) e^{-j \arg I_l}$$

$$I_k = \frac{1}{T_s} \int_0^{T_s} h(t) e^{-j2\pi kt/T_s} e^{j2\pi\epsilon(t)t} e^{j\phi(t)} dt \quad (2)$$

where n_k^l is white Gaussian noise in the l th channel at time k . In this paper, we assume, contrary to most previous approaches, that the carrier frequency offset and the carrier phase offset are *not* time-invariant. The fading behavior of the frequency offset is assumed to be given by

$$\epsilon_{k+1} = \alpha^\epsilon \epsilon_k + v_k^\epsilon, \quad (3)$$

where $\epsilon_k \triangleq \epsilon(kT_s)$ and the fading characteristics of the carrier phase noise are described by

$$\phi_{k+1} = \alpha^\phi \phi_k + v_k^\phi, \quad (4)$$

where $\phi_k \triangleq \phi(kT_s)$ and where v^ϵ, v^ϕ are Gaussian processes with standard deviations σ^ϵ and σ^ϕ , respectively. We assume the parameters $\alpha^\epsilon, \alpha^\phi$ to be *unknown* real constants.

Notation: Introduce the following notation. Let Y denote $\{\hat{c}_k^l; l = 0, 1, \dots, N-1, k = 0, 1, \dots, T\}$, y_k denote $\{\hat{c}_k^l; l = 0, 1, \dots, N-1\}$, θ denote $\{\alpha^\epsilon, \alpha^\phi\}$, X denote $\{\epsilon_k, \phi_k; k = 0, 1, \dots, T\}$, C denote $\{c_k^l; l = 0, 1, \dots, N-1, k = 0, 1, \dots, T\}$, C^l denote $\{c_k^l; k = 0, 1, \dots, T\}$, C_k denote $\{c_k^l; l = 0, 1, \dots, N-1\}$.

2.2 Objectives

The aim of this paper is to estimate the transmitted signals and unknown parameters, track the drift of

Figure 1: OFDM system

the frequency offset and the carrier phase noise in an OFDM system in a unified manner. We assume that the channel gain parameters, h , are known, but that the transmitted data and the parameters characterizing the fading are unknown and have to be estimated.

The objective of this paper is to suggest an off-line channel identification scheme, *i.e.*, given Y , it is desired to derive, in a MAP sense, a joint channel and parameter estimates of (X, θ) , *i.e.*,

$$(X, \theta)^{MAP} \triangleq \arg \max_{(X, \theta)} f(X, \theta | Y) \quad (5)$$

where $f(\cdot)$ is the probability density function. An EM based scheme that yields estimates of the time-varying channel is given in the following section. As a by-product of the expectation step of the proposed scheme, MAP estimates of the input signals are computed.

3 SCHEME FOR JOINT CARRIER PHASE AND FREQUENCY OFFSET TRACKING

We propose an iterative scheme that jointly, in a unified manner, tracks the fading characteristics of the frequency offset and of the carrier phase and also estimates the involved fading parameters and the transmitted data. Based on the assumptions made in the previous section on the fading characteristics, we now rewrite the OFDM system in a

state-space form.

Denote

$$\begin{aligned}
x_k &\triangleq [\phi_k, \epsilon_k]', \\
v_k &\triangleq [v_k^\phi, v_k^\epsilon]', \\
\Sigma_v &\triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \sigma^\phi & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma^\epsilon \end{bmatrix} \\
y_k &\triangleq [\hat{c}_k^0, \hat{c}_k^1, \dots, \hat{c}_k^{N-1}]', \\
g_k^l(\phi_k, \epsilon_k, C_k) &\triangleq c_k^l |I_l| + \sum_{m=0, m \neq k}^{N-1} c_m^l I_{n-m} e^{-j \arg I_l}, \\
w_k &\triangleq [n_k^0 e^{-j \arg I_0}, \dots, n_k^{N-1} e^{-j \arg I_{N-1}}]'
\end{aligned}$$

The state-space model of the OFDM system is then given by

$$\begin{aligned}
x_{k+1} &= \begin{bmatrix} \alpha^\epsilon & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha^\phi \end{bmatrix} x_k + v_k \\
y_k &= [g_k^0(\phi_k, \epsilon_k, C_k), \dots, g_k^{N-1}(\phi_k, \epsilon_k, C_k)]' + w_k
\end{aligned}$$

Assuming that the channel, h , over which the signals are transmitted and the carrier phase noise, ϕ , and the frequency offset, ϵ_k , are time-invariant over each sampling period T_s , we get

$$\begin{aligned}
I^l &= \frac{1}{T_s} \int_0^{T_s} h e^{-j2\pi l t / T_s} e^{j2\pi \epsilon t} e^{j\phi} dt \\
&= \frac{h e^{j\phi}}{j2\pi(T\epsilon - l)} (e^{j2\pi \epsilon T_s} - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

The proposed iterative scheme computes the joint, optimal in a MAP sense, state and parameter estimates of the system. The estimates are computed via the expectation conditional maximization (ECM) algorithm [9]. The ECM algorithm is an extension of the expectation maximization (EM) algorithm [10] and is an iterative method of extracting the mode of the posterior density. Also, as a by-product of the expectation step, the MAP estimates of the states u_k are obtained.

We now present a general description for the proposed scheme for computing the MAP estimate as defined in Eq. (5).

ECM algorithm:

0. Set $i = 1$. Determine the initial estimate $(X, \theta)^{(1)}$. Choose $\varepsilon > 0$.

1. Expectation Step:

Evaluate

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{Q}((X, \theta); (X, \theta)^{(i)}) &\triangleq \\
&\mathbb{E} \left\{ \ln f(Y, X, U, \theta) | Y, (X, \theta)^{(i)} \right\} \quad (6)
\end{aligned}$$

2. Conditional Maximization Steps:

Instead of maximizing (6) directly as a function of (X, θ) , the ECM algorithm updates some parameters sequentially by keeping the others fixed to their previous values. In particular, the state and parameters are updated in the following sequence:

a. Update of the Parameters of the Fading Characteristics:

Compute θ as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
\theta^{(i+1)} &= \\
&\arg \max_{\theta} \mathcal{Q}((X^{(i)}, \theta); (X, \theta)^{(i)}) \quad (7)
\end{aligned}$$

b. Update of the Carrier Phase and Frequency Offset:

Compute X as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
X^{(i+1)} &= \\
&\arg \max_X \mathcal{Q}((X, \theta^{(i+1)}); (X, \theta)^{(i)}) \quad (8)
\end{aligned}$$

3. $i := i + 1$. Iterate steps 1–3 until $\|(X, \theta)^{(i+1)} - (X, \theta)^{(i)}\| < \varepsilon$, where ε is some positive constant.

It turns out, that Step 2.b. in the Maximization step is given by applying an EKS to the system.

We now give the details of our proposed scheme:

Expectation Step:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{Q}((\theta, X); (\theta, X)^{(i)}) &\triangleq \mathbb{E} \left\{ \ln f(Y, C, X | \theta) | Y, (\theta, X)^{(i)} \right\} \\
&= -\frac{T}{2} \ln(2\pi\sigma_w^2) - \frac{T}{2} \ln(2\pi\sigma_v^2) \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^T \sum_{i_0, i_1, \dots, i_{N-1}=1}^M \left\{ \frac{(\epsilon_k - \alpha^\epsilon \epsilon_{k-1})^2}{(\sigma_v^\epsilon)^2} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{(\phi_k - \alpha^\phi \phi_{k-1})^2}{(\sigma_v^\phi)^2} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + (y_k - g(\epsilon_k, \phi_k, C_k))' \Sigma_w^{-2} (y_k - g(\epsilon_k, \phi_k, C_k)) \right\} \\
&\quad \times \Pr(c_k = i_0, c_{k-1} = i_1, \dots, c_{k-N+1} = i_{N-1} | Y, \theta)
\end{aligned}$$

The MAP estimate of the transmitted sequence of signals, c_k , are given by

$$\arg \max_C \Pr(c_k = i_0, c_{k-1} = i_1, \dots, c_{k-N+1} = i_{N-1} | Y, \theta)$$

The Maximization Steps:

We now give the update formulae of the state and parameter estimates.

- Compute the update of the parameter α^ϕ using the following Yule-Walker equation:

$$(\alpha^\phi)^{(i+1)} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^T \phi_k^{(i)} \phi_{k-1}^{(i)}}{\sum_{k=1}^T \phi_k^{(i)} \phi_k^{(i)}} \quad (9)$$

- Compute the update of the parameter α^ϵ using the following Yule-Walker equation:

$$(\alpha^\epsilon)^{(i+1)} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^T \epsilon_k^{(i)} \epsilon_{k-1}^{(i)}}{\sum_{k=1}^T \epsilon_k^{(i)} \epsilon_k^{(i)}} \quad (10)$$

- Compute the update of the carrier phase noise and the frequency offset via the EKS [11]:

$$\begin{aligned} G_k &= \frac{\partial g(k, X)}{\partial X} \Big|_{X=X_{k|k-1}} \\ &= \left[\frac{\partial g(k, X)}{\partial \epsilon}, \frac{\partial g(k, X)}{\partial \phi} \right] \Big|_{X=X_{k|k-1}} \\ K_k &= P_{k|k-1} G'_t \\ &\quad \times \left[G_k P_{k|k-1} G'_t + \Sigma_w^2 \right]^{-1} \\ \hat{X}_{k|k} &= \hat{X}_{k|k-1} + K_k \left[y_k - g(k, X_{k|k-1}) \right] \\ P_{k|k} &= P_{k|k-1} - P_{k|k-1} G'_t \\ &\quad \times \left[G_k P_{k|k-1} G'_t + \Sigma_w^2 \right]^{-1} \\ &\quad \times G_k P_{k|k-1} \\ \hat{X}_{k+1|k} &= \begin{bmatrix} (\alpha^\epsilon)^{(i)} & 0 \\ 0 & (\alpha^\phi)^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} X_{k|k} \\ P_{k|k+1} &= G_k P_{k|k} G'_t + \Sigma_v^2 \end{aligned}$$

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